

HERBAL CANDY –A FORMULATION OF HERBS

*Sanjana Julias Thilakar ,*Sanofer Fatima and **Poonam Sethi

*Assistant Professor, Department of Plant Biology and Plant Biotechnology The Ethiraj College for Women,Chennai

** Scholar, Department of Plant Biology and Plant Biotechnology, The Ethiraj College for Women,Chennai

** Assistant Professor, Department of Plant Biology and Plant Biotechnology Guru Nanak College,Chennai

ABSTRACT

A herbal candy was prepared from *Coleus amboinicus*Lour. (Mexicanmint), *Ocimum tenuiflorum* Linn. (Tulsi) and *Borassus flabellifer*Linn. (Palm candy powder). Screening for the presence of phytochemicals and estimation of the macromolecule in the herbalcandy. Later optimisation of the organoleptic characters and estimation of the antioxidant property ,In conclusion the Vitamin C content in the sample.

Key Words: Herbal Candy,antioxidant,phytochemical,Vitamin C

INTRODUCTION

Herbs and spices play a crucial role in medicinal applications,with ginger and tulsi being employed in the Indian system of medicinefor cold and cough. Utilizing candy as a rapid and efficient deliverysystem for medications, an investigation was undertaken to create

herbal candy employing a standardized method, incorporating gingeroil to enhance its medicinal value. Through the optimization of citricacid and ginger oil, hard-boiled sugar candy was developed. A gingeroil concentration of 2.5 percent yielded the maximum overallacceptability score (7.05), with slightly lower scores for color, textureand mouthfeel compared to herbal candy produced with 2.0 percentginger oil. Herbal candy prepared at 145°C exhibited the best hardness and sensory characteristics.

Children adore chocolate, but they typically dislike medicine. Thisstudy aims to create medicated chocolate by incorporating a herbaldrug, specifically the anti-tussive *Ocimum sanctum*(Tulsi), to combatcommon ailments like cough and viral infections in children. Theformulation involves an aqueous extract of Tulsi, providing antitussiveproperties. The resulting medicated chocolate undergoes evaluationfor factors such as general appearance, dimension, hardness, blooming test, drug content determination, and physical stability. (Yogesh S.Kolekar, et al., 2021)

The primary aim of this study is to create a nutritious chocolatewith antioxidant and anti-cancer properties, incorporating beneficialingredients such as *Ocimum sanctum* (Tulsi) for its medicinal qualitiesand black sesame for improved blood pressure and anti-aging benefits.The formulation

involves blending cocoa with finely powdered coconutsugar to produce a confectionery, aiming to enhance patient compliance and overall value. (Dhanashree R, et al., 2023)

Herbs like *Azadirachta indica* and *Bacopa monnieri*, known for their rich antioxidant content, along with nutrient-dense seeds, are incorporated into a herbal chocolate bar due to their bitter taste when consumed alone. The sensory panel approved the chocolate with herbs, with all samples having an acceptance index above 70%. (Reevika and Shweta, 2019)

MATERIALS AND METHOD

S.No. INGREDIENTS QUANTITY

01. *Coleus amboinicus* (Karpuravalli) 2 leaves
02. *Ocimum tenuiflorum* (Tulsi) 4 - 5 leaves
03. *Piper betle* (Betel) 1
04. *Borassus flabellifer* (Palm candy) 100 g
05. *Alpinia officinarum* (Sitharathai) Small piece
06. *Cinnamomum verum* (Cinnamon) 1
07. *Piper longum* (Thippili) Small piece
08. *Piper longum* (Kandan thippili) Small piece
09. *Elettaria cardamomum* (Cardamon) 1
10. *Syzygium aromaticum* (Clove) 4
11. *Piper cubeba* (Val milagu) 10
12. *Piper nigrum* (Pepper) 10
13. *Zingiber officinale* (Sukku powder) 1 pinch
14. Honey 1 tblsp
15. *Curcuma longa* (Turmeric powder) 2 pinch
16. *Glycyrrhiza glabra* (Liquorice powder) 1 pinch
17. *Acalypha indica* (Kuppaimeni powder) 1 pinch
18. *Cynodon dactylon* (Arugampul powder) 1 pinch
19. *Solanum trilobatum* (Thoothuvala powder) 2 pinch
20. *Solanum xanthocarpum* (Kandankathiri powder) 1 pinch

21. Phyllanthus emblica (Gooseberry powder) 2 pinch

PREPARATION

- Grind all wet (Karpuravalli, Tulsi, Betel) and dry (Sitharathai,
- Cinnamon, Thippili, Kandan thippili, Cardamon, Clove, Pepper,
- Val milagu) ingredients with water.
- Filter the mixture.
- In a kadai, add 100g of palm candy along with other powder
- and little water.
- Heat till it dissolves.
- Strain it and add to the mixture.
- Take a molding plate and apply oil or butter to it.
- Boil the mixture and check sugar syrup.
- Add 1 tblsp of honey after room temperature along with 12
- lemon.
- Add palm candy powder to avoid stickiness.
- Store it in a dry airtight container in a fridge.

PHYTOCHEMICAL TEST

For the phytochemical test and estimation, 1g of powdered candy was mixed in 10mL of water.

A) **ORGANOLEPTIC TEST** has high relevance on the quality of the product because it deals with direct contact with the consumer preferences. This method is easy and applicable.

B) **PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING** (J.B. Harborne, 1984)

The following tests were carried out individually for aqueous extract of herbal candy to detect various phyto constituents present in the extract.

1. CARBOHYDRATES :

MOLISCH TEST : Take 1mL aqueous candy extract. Few drops of Molisch's reagent is added to the test tube. Few drops of concentrated H₂SO₄ is added dropwise along the wall of the test tube. Purple to Red brown colour indicates the presence of carbohydrates in the sample.

FEHLING TEST : Take 1mL of aqueous candy extract. Add equal volumes of Fehling solution A and Fehling solution B. Heat it. Red precipitate indicates the presence of carbohydrates in the sample.

2. TERPENOIDS (CARDIAC GLYCOSIDES) :

SALKOWSKI TEST : Take 1mL of aqueous candy extract. To it, add 2mL of chloroform and 3mL of concentrated H₂SO₄. Reddish brown colour indicates the presence of terpenoids in the sample.

3. PHENOL

FERRIC CHLORIDE TEST :Take 50mg of extract and dissolve it in 5mL of distilled water. To it, add few drops of 5% ferric chloride solution. A dark green colour indicates the presence of phenolic compound in the sample

LEAD ACETATE TEST :Take 50mg of extract and dissolve it in 5mL of distilled water. To it, add 3mL of 10% lead acetate solution. Bulky white precipitate indicates the presence of phenolic compound in the sample.

4. ALKALOIDS :

DRAGENDORFF'S TEST :Take 1mL of aqueous candy extract. To it, add few drops of Dragendorff reagent. Orange brown precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids in the sample.

MAYER'S TEST :Take 1mL of aqueous candy extract. To it, add 2 drops of Mayer's reagent along the sides of the test tube. White creamy precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids in the sample.

5. FLAVANOIDS :

□ **FERRIC CHLORIDE TEST** :Take 1mL of aqueous candy extract. To it, add few drops of ferric chloride solution. Intense green colour indicates the presence of flavanoids in the sample.

6. PROTEINS :

BIURET TEST :Take 2mL of aqueous candy extract. To it, few drops of Biuret reagent is added. Purple colour indicates the presence of proteins in the sample.

MILLON'S TEST :Take 2mL of aqueous candy extract. To it, add few drops of Millon's reagent. White precipitate indicates the presence of proteins in the sample.

7. SAPONIN:

FOAM TEST :Take 1mL of aqueous candy extract. To it, add 1mL of distilled water. Shake it vigorously for 2 minutes. Foam indicates the presence of saponin in the sample.

8. TANNIN :

Take 0.5mL of aqueous candy extract. To it, add 10mL of bromine water. Decolouration of bromine water indicates the presence of tannin in the sample

C) VITAMIN C (ASCORBIC ACID) TEST

- To prepare 0.025% Dichloroindophenol solution, 0.025g dichloroindophenol is dissolved in 100mL of distilled water in a volumetric flask.
- Invert the volumetric flask several times.
- To prepare Vitamin C solution, 0.1 g L-ascorbic acid is

- dissolved in 100 mL distilled water.
- Measure 10 mL of 0.025% dichloroindophenol solution and
- transfer it into a test tube.
- Add Vitamin C solution dropwise, counting each drop added
- to test tube until the colour changes from blue to colourless
- or very light amber endpoint.
- Be sure to swirl the solution after each drop is added.
- Repeat the same procedure for the sample.

D) DPPH RADICAL SCAVENGING ACTIVITY:

The radical scavenging capacity of the aqueous extracts was measured based on DPPH (1,1-diphenyl 2-picrylhydrazyl) radical scavenging activity.

1. Preparation of the sample :

- Take 1g of powdered candy and to it add 25mL of 99%
- methanol.
- Cover the solution with aluminium foil.

2. Preparation of DPPH solution :

- Take 4mg DPPH and dissolve it in 100mL methanol.
- Keep it in a dark place.
- Fresh DPPH solution should be prepared at the time of
- experiment.

Procedure :

- Centrifuge the sample for 15 minutes at 6000 rpm.
- Extract the supernatant.
- Prepare a solution series using the extracted solution and methanol.
- Take 1mL from each sample and add 3mL of DPPH solution.
- Make up each solution with 99% methanol upto 10mL of conical flask.
- Keep the samples in dark for 30 minutes.
- Absorbance was measured at 517nm taking methanol as blank.
- Percent inhibition of DPPH radical was calculated by $A_{\text{blank}} - A_{\text{sample}}$

A blank where, $I\%$ = Inhibition of DPPH

A blank = Absorbance of control compound

A sample = Absorbance of test compound

RESULTS

A) ORGANOLEPTIC TEST :

Sensory evaluation parameters revealed that herbal candy is brown in colour, with a little sweet taste.

S.No. SENSORY PROPERTIES OBSERVATION

1 Colour Dark Brown

2 Odour Aromatic

3 Taste Little sweet

4 Texture Smooth

B) PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS :

The sample shows positive result in only carbohydrates and Terpenoids

S.No. CONSTITUENTS INFERENCE

1 Carbohydrates -Present

2 Terpenoids Present

3 Phenols Absent

4 Alkaloids Absent

5 Flavanoids Absent

6 Protein Absent

7 Saponin Absent

8 Tannin Absent

C) VITAMIN - C :

Vitamin C is important nutritionally. It is believed that high doses of Vitamin C has a positive effect on the immune system and help in combating common cold. Using Vitamin C solution as standard, the amount of Vitamin C in sample is calculated. If it takes 11 drops of Vitamin C solution and 121 drops of sample to neutralise 10 mL of dichloroindophenol solution, the calculations are as follows : $(\text{Drops standard})(\text{Concentration standard}) =$

$(\text{Drops unknown})(\text{Concentration unknown})(11 \text{ drops}) (100 \text{ mg}/100 \text{ mL of Vitamin C}) = (121 \text{ drops}) (\text{nmg of Vitamin C}/100 \text{ mL of sample})$ $n = 9.09 \text{ mg of Vitamin C}$ Therefore, the concentration of Vitamin C in the sample is 9.09 mg/100 mL

E) ANTI OXIDANT ACTIVITY :

The antioxidant activity of candy was determined using the DPPH free radical scavenging activity. The results are shown in table and figure. We can conclude that the scavenging effect of the extract is gradually increasing.

S.No. CONCENTRATION ABSORBANCE INHIBITION %

(mg/mL)

1 0.1 27

2 0.3 36

3 0.5 54

4 0.7 63

5 0.9 27

DISCUSSION

In conclusion, herbal candies for cough and cold can be a natural and soothing alternative to conventional remedies. The blend of medicinal herbs in these candies, such as Coleus, Betel, Tulsi, Liquorice, Ginger, and Honey, may offer relief from symptoms like sore throat and cough while providing a pleasant and palatable experience. Additionally, the immune-boosting properties of certain herbs can contribute to the overall efficacy of herbal candies in supporting the body's defense against respiratory infections. Overall, the appeal of herbal candies lies in their potential to offer relief with no side effects, making them a popular choice for those seeking natural alternatives

for respiratory health. In conclusion, herbal candies for cough and cold can be a natural and soothing alternative to conventional remedies.

The blend of medicinal herbs in these candies, such as Coleus, Betel, Tulsi, Liquorice, Ginger, and Honey, may offer relief from symptoms like sore throat and cough while providing a pleasant and palatable experience. Additionally, the immune-boosting properties of certain herbs can contribute to the overall efficacy of herbal candies in supporting the body's defense against respiratory infections. Overall, the appeal of herbal candies lies in their potential to offer relief with no side effects, making them a popular choice for those seeking natural alternatives for respiratory health

SUMMARY

Collection of leaves was from the terrace (house) and powders were from Rani Naatu Marandu Kadai, West Mambalam. # Different proportions were made to formulate the herbal drug. Qualitative analysis was performed and showed it has presence of carbohydrates and terpenoids. # Organoleptic test was done. # Estimation of carbohydrates was done as per the standard procedure which showed the presence of carbohydrates in appreciable quantity. Antioxidant test was conducted with DPPH radical scavenging activity. # Drug content

determination was observed and both Rf value of control and test are the same. # Vitamin C was estimated and the herbal candy contains 9.09 mg of Vitamin C

REFERENCES

1. Dhanashree R. Thakare and Priyanka G. Dhumal, Preparation and evaluation of herbal chocolate, International journal of advanced research in science, communication and technology, Volume 3, Issue 8, May 2023
2. Ghuge Jagannath Ramprasad, Kale Vidya Raosaheb, Formulation and evaluation of antidiabetic chocolate by using guava leaves and mulberry fruits, International journal for multidisciplinary research, Volume 5, Issue 1, January-February 2023
3. Harborne, J.B. (1984) Textbook of Phytochemical Methods. A Guide to Modern Techniques of Plant Analysis. 2nd Edition, Chapman and Hall Ltd, London.
4. Madhuri Patil, Abhay Raizaday, Varsha Raut, Formulation and evaluation of herbal candy based on Indian medicinal plants for cancer therapy via immunomodulation, SGVU journal of pharmaceutical research & education, 2020, 5 (2), 562-573
5. Mahendra Dwivedi, K.K Jha, Swati Pandey, Ankush Sachan, Himanshu Sharma, Shloke Kumar Dwivedi, Formulation and evaluation of herbal medicated chocolate in treatment of intestinal worms and related problems, International journal of food and nutritional science, Volume 11, S Iss 2, 2022
6. Pothu R and Yamsani MR. Lozenges Formulation and Evaluation: A review. IJAPR, Vol11, 2014: 290-294
7. Preeti Shukla, Suresh Bhise and Balaji Gaikwad, Development of herbal candy using ginger essential oil, Journal of Postharvest technology, 2018
8. Reddy Sunil, K. Mounika, A. Venkatesham, Design and fabrication of medicated chocolate formulation by chocolate drug delivery system, Int J Curr Pharm Res, 2017
9. Reevika Khurana and Shweta Singh, Formulation of a herbal bar with muskmelon and sunflower seed, The pharma innovation journal 2019;8(5): 81-85
10. Rohini Chandratte, Kulsumfatima Khan, Mansi Patel, Harshala More, Prachi Mehendale, Preparation and evaluation of herbal cough lozenges : corid-cough pearls, International journal of pharma O2, Volume 2, Issue 2, March - April 2020
- Sachin B. Narkhede, Shailesh V. Luhar, Neha S. Vadgama, Jenil S. Patel, Jeny J. Patel, Khushi K. Patel, Lubnabanu S. Patel, Noopur K. Patel, Preparation and evaluation of medicated herbal candy of mahua for sore throat, International journal of research and development, Volume 8, Issue 5, May 2023 12.
- Sharma Mayank and Jain Dinesh Kumar, Chocolate formulation as drug delivery system for pediatrics, Indonesian J. Pharm, 2012; 23(4): 216-224 13.
- Shivani A. Chaudhari, Rohini R. Devare, Prajakta S. Dewang, Varsha B Patil, Amruta M. Patil, Dr. Sunil P. Pawar, Chocolate formulation as drug delivery system, Indian Journal of Drugs, 2018; 6(2): 136-141
14. Sivalalitha. Pyla, B. Nagamani, Suvarna Kasi, PV Madhavi Latha, P. Umadevi, Formulation and evaluation of anti-hypertensive herbal chocolate, Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res., 80(2), May - June 2023
15. Umashankar MS, Dinesh SR, Rini R, Lakshmi KS and Damodharan N. Chewable Lozenge Formulation: A review. Int Res J Pharm, Vol7(4), 2014: 09-16

PLATES

FIGURE 1 : *Piperbetle* and Palm candy

FIGURE II: Herbal candy

